

Webtoon-based online comics in measuring the Pancasila student profile at Madrasah Tsanawiyah in Riau Province

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ABSTRACT

The objectives of the Pancasila student profile are a number of characters and competencies that are expected to be achieved by students, which are based on the noble values of Pancasila. The purpose of this article is to measure the Pancasila student profile at Madrasah Tsanawiyah (MTs) Riau Province, Indonesia and to find out its effect through the use of webtoon-based online comics. This study conducted a quantitative descriptive approach and focus group discussions in six State MTs. The research instrument used in this study was a Pancasila student profile questionnaire, which was distributed to students. The findings showed the six indicators and their implementation in each madrasa. The six MTs in this study were categorized as very good, which indicated the need to increase Pancasila student profile. There are considerable disparities in indices of religion, fear of God Almighty, and noble character, global variety, mutual collaboration, independence, critical thinking, and creativity for Pancasila student profile policies. The use of webtoon-based online comics in measuring the Pancasila student profile is based on madrasa policy and it has not been thoroughly tested in all MTs in Riau Province. Furthermore, it can consider its use in a wider Madrasah Tsanawiyah frame. MTs in Indonesia can measure the Pancasila student profile through the use of webtoon-based online comics to achieve student character standards that are in line with educational goals in Indonesia. This research provides a webtoon-based online comic framework to measure the Pancasila student profile.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Character is something that exists in every living being. The form of character possessed by each individual is very diverse, and each individual has characteristics that describe the attitudes, character, behavior and differences of each individual [1]–[3]. The nation's civilization can be built properly and successfully if most of the people have strong, positive and resilient characters, but if most of the people have

negative characters it can result in the civilization being built to weaken [4]–[6]. Strengthening values at a time when everyone is very important, including the value of character education [7]–[9]. In Indonesia, character education is currently being discussed a lot. This is because character education is one of the government's efforts to improve the quality of education. Character education is an effort to educate children so that they can make smart decisions and practice them in everyday life so that they can have a positive impact on their environment [10]–[12]. This shows that improving the quality of student character formation is very important [13]–[15]. Thus, education in Indonesia does not only develop knowledge intelligence but comprehensive intelligence, namely teachers must be able to construct learning as a means of developing knowledge intelligence as well as the personality or character of students.

But in reality, the problem that has recently surfaced in the world of education is the problem of moral degradation. The Indonesian Child Protection Commission (ICPC) investigation found that the number of fights in Indonesia increased in 2018, from 1.1,000 in previous years. Based on ICPC data that in 2020 the number of bullying cases contributed to children's problems [16]–[18]. There are still many cases of rape against children or students which show that the country is facing a multidimensional crisis. As an alternative in dealing with multidimensional crises, the government has formulated a policy of cultural and national character education [19]–[22]. Furthermore, the fall in values, ethics, and manners leads to a deterioration in cultural education and the character of the Indonesian people [23]–[25]. As a result, we can see that character development is a fundamental requirement in the nation-building process, because only a nation with strong character will endure as a nation. Character education and Pancasila education are two efforts that may be made to improve the character of pupils in order to create a superior.

The Minister of Education and Culture said that strengthening the formation of the character of students can be achieved through various steps of the Ministry of Education and Culture which are focused on efforts to achieve *Pancasila* student profile from basic training to university studies. *Pancasila* student profile are one of the manifestations of lifelong learning for students in Indonesia who are able to have global competencies and behave based on the values of Pancasila as the basis of the Indonesian state [26]–[29]. Pancasila student profile have six main characteristics, namely: piety and faith in God as well as noble character, mutual cooperation, independent, creative, critical reasoning, and global diversity [30]–[32]. It was also stated that in addition to various actions that resulted in the formation of profiles of Pancasila students, the mechanism for character building socialization with content was carried out to educational units, families and communities which was coordinated with strengthening the character of the Ministry of Education and Culture Center [33], [34]. The dimensions of the Pancasila Profile are what teachers expect to be able to implement in the learning process (planning, implementation, and assessment) of learning. One of the media that can be used to cultivate the character of students who have the Pancasila Student indicator is through webtoon-based online comics.

Webtoon is an online comic service provider platform that can be read for free by everyone. Webtoon is the most popular online comic provider application in Indonesia [35]–[37]. This is because webtoon is the only online comic platform that provides comics to be read for free in five languages, namely Korean, Japanese, Thai, English, and also Indonesian. The popularity of webtoons has been rooted in beginner comics. Webtoon readers who have reached millions of readers put this comic content easily spread massively in a short time. Readers can immediately give an assessment and comment on the comics they read. Webtoon as an online comic platform can be used as a supporting media to reach more target audiences [37]–[39]. Besides that, webtoon-based comics are also able to shape the character of students [40], [41]. Character formation starts from oneself when a teacher can imitate good behavior or character towards students in the school environment [42]–[44]. The correlation between personality and visual elements in the image, it makes it easier for the audience to receive the information displayed (the impression of violence, strength, life) [45]–[47]. The results of the study [48], [49] are using the online comic to convey the character values of Pancasila students in the current era of disruption, namely by using rules in the discussion room so that there is an exchange of ideas, joint decision making with mutual respect, responsibility, freedom and consideration.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

This study aims to determine the Pancasila student profile at Madrasah Tsanawiyah (MTs) in Riau Province, Indonesia and to determine its effect through the use of webtoon-based online comics. The Pancasila student profile indicator is used in accordance with Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture Number 22 of 2020 about the Ministry of Education and Culture's Strategic Plan for the Years 2020-2024. Therefore, this study measures the Pancasila student profile in the use of webtoon-based online comics that aim to support the improvement of the character of students. The steps taken in using webtoon-based online comics include: i) The teacher divides students into six groups with a total of seven students per

group; ii) The teacher distributes webtoon-based online comics about today's junior high school students which contain indicators of Pancasila student profiles as learning media to each group; iii) The teacher guides and encourages students to read and understand the comics that have been distributed; iv) The teacher distributes student worksheets to work on in groups by understanding the contents of the comics; v) Each group carries out the tasks given by the teacher, namely: each group works together in working on the student worksheet that have been distributed; vi) The teacher provides guidance to students or groups in working on student worksheet; vii) The teacher guides and encourages students to read the results of the worksheets they have worked on; viii) Each group is asked to send one a student as a representative to read the results of the student worksheet that has been done; ix) Each group member or student is given the opportunity to ask questions about material that has not been understood; and x) The teacher straightens out misunderstandings and provides reinforcement about ongoing learning.

The *Pancasila* student profile framework is used to assess the extent of consumption of webtoon-based online comics with appropriate quality assurance. As a result, indicators are required to analyze these requirements in order to satisfy them. To pick indicators, this study evaluates various past studies. Table 1 shows the evolution of indicators and statement items based on six indicators examined in this study: faith, fear of God Almighty, noble character, global variety, mutual cooperation, independence, critical thinking, and creativity.

Table 1. Development of the Pancasila student profile grid

No	Variable	Indicator	Description	Number of items
1	Pancasila student profile	Have faith, fear God Almighty, and have a noble character	Indonesian students who believe, fear God Almighty, and have noble character are students who have good morals in relation to God Almighty. He understands the teachings of his religion and beliefs and applies this understanding in his daily life.	13
		Global diversity	Indonesian students maintain their noble culture, locality and identity, and keep an open mind in interacting with other cultures, so as to foster a sense of mutual respect and the possibility of forming a noble culture that is positive and does not conflict with the nation's noble culture.	11
		Worked together	Indonesian students have the ability to work together, namely the ability to carry out activities together voluntarily so that the activities carried out can run smoothly, easily and lightly.	10
		Independent	Indonesian students are independent students, namely students who are responsible for their learning processes and outcomes.	10
		Critical reasoning	Students who think critically are able to objectively process both qualitative and quantitative information, build relationships between various information, analyze information, evaluate and conclude it.	10
		Creative	Creative students are able to modify and produce something original, meaningful, useful, and impactful.	10

The sample of this study was State MTs in Riau Province which did not have a policy of strengthening the *Pancasila* student profile as many as six MTs consisting of 385 students. MTs as the organizers of the policy to strengthen the *Pancasila* student profile in Riau Province are responsible for monitoring the sustainability of the policy. Furthermore, non-probability sampling was utilized in this study, which was specifically appointed by the researcher to join this study since it did not have a strategy of reinforcing the Pancasila student profile. To comprehend the problem of student character, a purposive sample assessment was utilized to identify precise information on Madrasah Tsanawiyah based on the policy of strengthening the *Pancasila* student profile and decision makers [50].

To verify the Pancasila student profile instrument, statistical testing was performed. There are several tests available, such as normal testing, validity tests, and reliability tests [51], [52]. The adoption of the *Pancasila* student profile is then carried out in stages, including: *Pancasila* student profile measurement. The *Pancasila* student profile at MTs was measured using online surveys and reinforced via focus group discussions. The factors were graded on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The criteria are used to assess the level of implementation of the *Pancasila* student profile enhancement program. The *Pancasila* student profile is measured by the value of each indicator, the percentage of the *Pancasila* student profile for each variable, and the overall impact of the *Pancasila* student profile implementation. This attempts to assess the implementation of the *Pancasila* student profile, as well as the variables that must be adjusted by the madrasa. Table 2 shows the interpretation of the *Pancasila* student profile conducted in MTs Riau Province [31].

Table 2. Interpretation of *Pancasila* student profile

Percentage (%)	Information
0% - 20%	“Not good”
21% - 40%	“Not good”
41% - 60%	“Pretty good”
61% - 80%	“Well”
81% - 100%	“Very good”

The Mann-Whitney U test was employed in this study to examine the influence of the variable employing webtoon-based online comics on the *Pancasila* student profile in six distinct Madrasah Tsanawiyah. This discovery also shows that the significance value, or asymp sig. (two-sided), must be smaller than 0.05. As a result, the hypothesis is accepted, implying that there are substantial variations in the factors of utilizing webtoon-based online comics in the six Madrasah Tsanawiyah. The Mann-Whitney U test was used to assess the degree of policy differences [53]. This study found that the orientation of the *Pancasila* student profile is one way to increase the use of webtoon-based online comics by using the Mann-Whitney U test.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Development of *Pancasila* student profile instruments

The study instrument consists of six indicators, each of which has 64 statements. The validity test findings for these six Madrasah Tsanawiyah were certified valid since all instrument points were greater than 0.3. Furthermore, the Cronbach’s alpha value must be larger than 0.6, with each value indicating markers of faith, piety to God Almighty, and noble character of 0.984; global variety of 0.954; mutual collaboration of 0.809; independence of 0.941; critical thinking of 0.884; and creative of 0.892. The normality test was then performed since the significance value was greater than 0.05. The significant value of the indicator of religion, fear of God, and noble character is 0.605; global variety is 0.549; mutual collaboration is 0.542; independence is 0.419; critical thinking is 0.488; and creativity is 0.598. As a result, the six indicators are assumed to be regularly distributed.

3.2. Implementation of webtoon-based online comic utilization in strengthening *Pancasila* student profiles

The use of webtoon-based online comics to boost the *Pancasila* student profile in six countries Madrasah Tsanawiyah was evaluated based on indicators such as faith, fear of God Almighty, and noble character, worldwide variety, mutual collaboration, independence, critical thinking, and innovation. Figure 1 shows the implementation of the use of webtoon-based online comics in strengthening the *Pancasila* student profile in this case study.

Figure 1. Student profile diagram of *Pancasila* students by Madrasah Tsanawiyah

Figure 1 shows that the overall use of webtoon-based online comics in strengthening the *Pancasila* student profile at MTs N 1 Kampar is better than other Madrasah Tsanawiyah. At MTs N 1 Kampar, indicators of faith, piety to God Almighty, and noble character reached 80.75% for the *Pancasila* student profile. This means that MTs N 1 Kampar under the guidance of the Regional Office of the Ministry of Religion of Riau Province has good character towards indicators of faith, fear of God Almighty, and noble character in the form of religious activities. However, the independent indicator is the lowest because of the motivation, interest in learning, the attitude of the child received from the family, especially the parents and the surrounding environment.

The Riau province ministry of religion coordinates the policy level for measuring *Pancasila* student profiles. These six madrassas collaborate with the Riau Province Regional Office, which is the policy-making agency. As a result, establishing the amount of variation in the policy of assessing the *Pancasila* student profile in these six places is required in order to give educational counsel to Madrasah Tsanawiyah. The Mann-Whitney U-test was used for the tests, which are reported in Tables 3 to 5.

Table 3. Descriptive statistics of *Pancasila* student profile

Indicator	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Have faith, fear God, and have noble character	385	79.19	5.974	12	84
Global diversity	385	69.65	6.733	11	77
Worked together	385	64.55	5.926	10	70
Independent	385	63.34	6.187	10	70
Critical reasoning	385	63.07	6.135	34	70
Creative	385	62.93	6.409	25	70

Table 4. Comparison of ratings from Madrasah Tsanawiyah

Indicator	Madrasah Tsanawiyah	N	Mean rank	Sum of ranks
Have faith, fear God, and have noble character	MTsN 1 Kampar	104	68.23	7095.50
	MTs N 1 Kota Pekanbaru	22	41.16	905.50
	MTs N 1 Pelalawan	34	58.71	1996.00
	MTs N 1 Siak	82	58.41	4790.00
	MTs N 2 Kuantan Singingi	51	66.47	3390.00
Global diversity	MTs N 3 Pekanbaru	92	75.07	6906.00
	MTsN 1 Kampar	104	66.88	6956.00
	MTs N 1 Kota Pekanbaru	22	47.50	1045.00
	MTs N 1 Pelalawan	34	46.43	1578.50
	MTs N 1 Siak	82	63.51	5207.50
Worked together	MTs N 2 Kuantan Singingi	51	67.35	3435.00
	MTs N 3 Pekanbaru	92	74.58	6861.00
	MTsN 1 Kampar	104	67.67	7038.00
	MTs N 1 Kota Pekanbaru	22	43.77	963.00
	MTs N 1 Pelalawan	34	50.74	1725.00
Independent	MTs N 1 Siak	82	61.72	5061.00
	MTs N 2 Kuantan Singingi	51	71.34	3638.50
	MTs N 3 Pekanbaru	92	72.36	6657.50
	MTsN 1 Kampar	104	67.48	7018.00
	MTs N 1 Kota Pekanbaru	22	44.68	983.00
Critical reasoning	MTs N 1 Pelalawan	34	54.16	1841.50
	MTs N 1 Siak	82	60.30	4944.50
	MTs N 2 Kuantan Singingi	51	70.02	3571.00
	MTs N 3 Pekanbaru	92	73.10	6725.00
	MTs N 1 Kampar	104	65.46	6808.00
Creative	MTs N 1 Kota Pekanbaru	22	54.23	1193.00
	MTs N 1 Pelalawan	34	52.26	1777.00
	MTs N 1 Siak	82	61.09	5009.00
	MTs N 2 Kuantan Singingi	51	67.39	3437.00
	MTs N 3 Pekanbaru	92	74.55	6859.00
	MTsN 1 Kampar	104	67.33	7002.50
	MTs N 1 Kota Pekanbaru	22	45.39	998.50
	MTs N 1 Pelalawan	34	51.56	1753.00
	MTs N 1 Siak	82	61.38	5033.00
	MTs N 2 Kuantan Singingi	51	66.75	3404.00
	MTs N 3 Pekanbaru	92	74.91	6892.00

According to Table 5, the indicators of faith, fear of God Almighty, and noble character have values of $U=652.5$ and $W=905.5$. When translated to Z , the value is -3.369 . The significance threshold is thus 0.001 . If the significance level or p -value is less than 5% (0.05), the null hypothesis can be rejected. As a result, there is a considerable disparity between the six Madrasah Tsanawiyah, or H_1 is approved. Global variety, mutual collaboration, independence, critical thinking, and creativity are many factors that differ greatly in the policy of gauging the Pancasila student profile.

Table 5. Test the output statistics of the Mann–Whitney U-test

	Indicator 1	Indicator 2	Indicator 3	Indicator 4	Indicator 5	Indicator 6
Mann-Whitney U	652.500	792.000	710.000	730.000	940.000	745.500
Wilcoxon W	905.500	1045.000	963.000	983.000	1193.000	998.500
Z	-3.369	-2.290	-2.869	-2.680	-1.332	-2.611
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.022	.004	.007	.018	.009

The results showed that the average success Pancasila student profile in SMP/MTs Riau Province was 90.26% with the “Very good” category, because the results of the analysis were 90.26% which were in the range of 81 – 100% . This success may be recognized through six indicators: faith, fear of God Almighty, and noble character; global variety; collaboration; independence; critical reasoning; and creativity.

3.2.1. Indicator of faith, fear of God Almighty, and noble character

Based on the results of the questionnaire distribution obtained, it can be seen that in the indicators of faith, fear of God Almighty, and noble character, an average percentage of 93.68% is obtained in the “very good” category because it is in the range of 81 – 100% . In the indicator of faith, fear of God Almighty, and noble character, the score is 93.18% with the category “Very good”. The first indicator gets the highest percentage score, it is because the practice of students’ religious values can be categorized as good. As a citizen in Indonesia, of course, you are required to have beliefs in accordance with the legalized religion, the religious teachings adopted by every citizen have been nurtured since childhood. The practice of students’ religious values is always developed through all kinds of school activities, these activities are always associated with religious values and noble character, such as when praying and being polite. The cultivation of religious characters is carried out by integrating cultural values into the implementation of student self-development programs in the implementation of learning in schools [54]–[56].

In addition, the factor that causes the increase in students’ religious values is habituation in the home environment, parents who direct their children well in embracing religion will of course have a good understanding of religion and morals [25], [57]. Factors that support the implementation of the formation of students’ religious character through habituation of religious activities, support from parents of students, commitment with school members and adequate facilities [11], [58]. Of course, the factors that have been described support the highest score percentage from the first aspect of the *Pancasila* student profile.

3.2.2. Global diversity indicator

Based on the results of the questionnaire distribution obtained, it can be seen that in the global Diversity indicator, an average percentage of 90.46% is obtained with the “very good” category because it is in the range of 81 – 100% . In the indicator of global diversity, the score is 89.75% with the category “Very good”. The second indicator gets the second highest percentage score of the six aspects of the Pancasila student profile. Students’ understanding of differences and diversity in schools can be categorized as good. The influencing factor of appreciating the diversity of students in the class is of course due to the interactions that occur during the learning process in the classroom. The learning process carried out is not limited to differences in ethnicity, race, or religion. An understanding of what students really need to reflect in the classroom, requires a variety of strategies for students to increase the value of diversity such as discussions, observations, case studies, simulations and role playing [59]–[61]. In addition, the guidance and examples provided by the teacher are factors that can increase students’ understanding of diversity, the teacher exemplifies how attitudes and behavior in respecting diversity [62]–[64]. Teachers foster diverse principles in children by educating in courteous manner and never bringing up sensitive themes such as religion and racial differences [65]–[67].

3.2.3. Mutual cooperation indicator

Based on the results of the questionnaire distribution obtained, it can be seen that in the mutual cooperation indicator, an average percentage of 91.88% is obtained with the “very good” category because it is in the range of 81 – 100% . In the indicator of mutual cooperation, the score is 91.16% with the “Very good”

category. The third indicator gets the third highest score percentage of the six aspects of the Pancasila student profile. There are several factors that lead to the practice of gotong royong from students, namely from the learning process. The teacher conditions a class so that students can work together with each other, from the program created by the teacher it will cause students to socialize with friends around and collaborate with group friends to complete assignments. The teacher's strategy in instilling mutual cooperation character attitudes such as giving direct examples to students, giving rewards in the form of praise so that the students' spirit of mutual cooperation is in line with the goals of education in schools [68]–[70]. Furthermore, the factors that can affect the understanding of students' values in mutual cooperation are student activities outside of class hours or extracurricular activities, there are several extracurricular activities that emphasize teamwork in groups such as scouts.

Extracurricular activities train students to work together in a group and train cohesiveness. By participating in extracurricular activities, it will familiarize students in collaborating with all friends [71]–[73]. To put forward the cultivation of the formation of national character values to students more effectively through scout extracurricular activities by prioritizing the value of cooperation, love to help, so that mutual cooperation character education is able to change behavior, ways of thinking and ways of acting to make students better and integrated [74]–[76].

3.2.4. Standalone indicator

Based on the results of the questionnaire distribution obtained, it can be seen that in the independent indicator, an average percentage of 90.59% is obtained with the “very good” category because it is in the range of 81–100%. In the independent indicator, it gets a score of 89.83% with the “Very good” category. In the fourth indicator, the Pancasila student profile has the third lowest score percentage of the six aspects. There are several factors that influence the independent character of each student. One of the factors is encouragement from the family, especially parents, parents condition students to be able to do many things individually such as completing homework and habituation.

Furthermore, the school environment factor, in the school environment students are expected to increase independence with a learning process designed by the teacher and be responsible for the tasks given to students. Factors that can affect the development of independent character of students are the family environment, school environment and community environment [63], [77], [78]. Therefore, self-regulation influences student learning independence somewhat, and self-regulation and discipline influence student learning independence concurrently [79]–[81].

3.2.5. Critical reasoning indicator

Based on the results of the questionnaire distribution obtained, it can be seen that in the critical reasoning indicator, an average percentage of 90.36% is obtained with the “very good” category because it is in the range of 81–100%. In the critical reasoning indicator, the score is 89.23% with the category “Very good”. The critical reasoning indicator gets the lowest percentage score of the six aspects of the *Pancasila* student profile. There are several factors that can affect students' critical reasoning abilities, first from within students which are influenced by students' ability to reason and students' motivation to use reasoning skills in solving a problem. In addition, there are factors that are influenced from outside of students such as the condition of the student's social environment at school, student behavior in responding to a problem and the family environment.

Factors that affect students' critical thinking skills are psychological learning factors which include intellectual development, motivation, and anxiety, physiological factors which include physical conditions, learning independence factors, and interaction factors [82]–[84]. From the results of the research, the percentage score for the lowest critical reasoning aspect of the other six aspects, this describes that there are some students who have not implemented the character of critical reasoning well, the ability of students to reason about a problem has not been carried out optimally. Not all students are able to develop in accordance with the school's goals or vision and mission to develop humans with independent thinking in critical thinking; students' low ability to think critically in learning is due to a lack of a learning process that directs students to think critically to solve a problem [85]–[87].

3.2.6. Creative indicator

Based on the results of the questionnaire distribution obtained, it can be seen that in the creative indicator, an average percentage of 83.87% is obtained with the “very good” category because it is in the range of 81–100%. Based on this information, the average success of the student Pancasila student profile is 90.26%. The interpretation of the success of the Pancasila student profile concluded that the success of the Pancasila student profile was classified as “Very good”, because the results of the analysis were 90.26% which were in the range of 81–100%.

On the creative indicator, it gets a score of 76.53% with the “Very good” category. The creative indicator gets the second lowest score among the six aspects of the *Pancasila* student profile. The problems seen in elementary schools are that learning has not been able to optimize the creativity process in students and most students cannot recognize their potential, teachers should be able to understand the creativity potential of students so that it can be optimized in the learning process [88]–[90]. However, the percentage score obtained is still in the good category, so that students' interest in creativity and creating new ideas is at a good level. The creative thinking profile of elementary school students in solving a problem on fluent thinking skills is sparking many new ideas in solving problems with sufficient ability [91], [92].

Based on the results, *Pancasila* student profile in MTs Riau Province can be qualified well and sufficiently in every aspect. This finding is reinforced by the findings of previous researchers who stated that the *Pancasila* student profile in the learning process can be character education for students and is relevant in every learning process [93]–[95]. By having good ethics, behaving positively, and participating in learning well according to the values of *Pancasila*, it will be a contribution for students in the effort to defend the state [96]–[98]. The advantage of this research is to analyze the *Pancasila* student profile in the effort to defend the state in MTs in a quantitative and qualitative descriptive manner in every aspect. With this research, it is hoped that every school can pay attention to the practice of *Pancasila* values in students in the *Pancasila* student profile as a form of character education. The implication of this research is to provide references for teachers related to the inculcation of *Pancasila* values in the application of the *Pancasila* student profile to students in the school environment and community. This research is limited to the results of descriptive analysis of *Pancasila* student profile data, so it is hoped that other researchers can develop research related to the influence of the *Pancasila* student profile in various situations in schools.

4. CONCLUSION

The results of this research showed that the *Pancasila* student profile instrument consists of six indicators, each of which has 64 valid and reliable statements. The use of webtoon-based online comics in strengthening *Pancasila* student profiles showed varying success among the Madrasah Tsanawiyah studied, with MTs N 1 Kampar having the highest success rate. However, the use of webtoon-based online comics in several indicators such as independence, critical thinking and creativity still needs improvement. The implication of this research is that the use of webtoon-based online comics can be an effective tool in strengthening student character within the *Pancasila* framework, and recommendations for further research are to more deeply understand the factors that influence the implementation and long-term impact of the use of this technology in character education. student.

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